

Khan Academy as a Supplementary Tool in Trigonometry: Effectiveness on Students' Performance

Robert I. Panco ^{a*}, Mary Jane J. Valila ^a and Allan J. Valila ^a

^a Department of Teacher Education, University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Campus, Laoang, Northern Samar, Philippines.

Authors' contributions

This work was carried out in collaboration among all authors. The researchers designed the study, performed the statistical analysis and wrote the first draft of the manuscript. The researchers managed the analyses of the study. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Abstract

This study investigated the effectiveness of Khan Academy as a supplementary tool in enhancing the performance of Grade 9 students in solving non-right triangles in trigonometry. Conducted at the University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Laboratory High School during the school year 2024-2025, the study employed a quasi-experimental design using both quantitative and qualitative approaches. A 15-item test, which was patterned from the DepEd module for Mathematics 9 focusing on illustrating the Law of Sines and Cosines, was used to assess students' understanding, with 29 participants divided into two groups: 14 students following traditional instruction and the other 15 students using Khan Academy as a supplement. The pre-test results showed no significant difference between the two groups, wherein both groups initially performed

*Corresponding author: Email: itsmepanco2003@gmail.com;

poorly. However, significant improvement was observed in the post-test scores of both groups, although there was no significant difference between the outcomes of traditional instruction and the Khan Academy intervention. Also, the thematic analysis of students' feedback highlighted challenges in using Khan Academy, including difficulties in navigation, content accessibility, assessments, and technical issues. Students also reported varied user experiences and suggested improvements such as enhancing technical stability, refining educational content, and increasing accessibility and learning flexibility.

Keywords: Khan academy; trigonometry; non-right triangles; supplementary learning tool; student performance.

1 Introduction

Trigonometry stands as a cornerstone of mathematics, integral to the academic curriculum. Its fundamental concepts extend to other disciplines such as geometry, algebra, and calculus. The broad applications of trigonometry illustrate its significance beyond the classroom. Mastering this subject equips students with versatile problem-solving skills and opens doors to numerous career opportunities. However, despite its significance, many students find trigonometry, specifically, solving non-right triangles, very challenging (Tyata et. al, 2021). Thus, building the foundations of trigonometric concepts for students is essential, especially for secondary students, as it will help them understand more abstract mathematical concepts and they can use their problem-solving skills when they get into college or higher education (Orhani, 2024).

Many students struggle with fundamental math concepts, particularly in trigonometry, leading to difficulties in problem solving. These difficulties in trigonometry were attributed to a lack of prior knowledge and experience with trigonometry, insufficient practice and review, and difficulty in visualizing and understanding abstract trigonometry concepts (Velez et al., 2023). Further, a study by Arhin et al (2021) found that conceptual difficulties were more common than principal and procedural difficulties. Students often rely on familiar right triangle methods and struggle with complex calculations, leading to errors when applying specific laws. Visualization challenges also contribute to these difficulties.

Students often struggle with solving non-right triangles in trigonometry because they rely too heavily on familiar right triangle methods and lack a solid grasp of the Law of Sines and Law of Cosines (Sosa et. al, 2024). Complex calculations can feel overwhelming, especially with the ambiguous case, where two possible solutions exist, making it difficult to determine the correct approach (Coddling et. al, 2024). Many students attempt to break non-right triangles into right triangles, which can lead to errors when the specific laws of trigonometry must be applied (Alfitri et. al, 2024). Visualization challenges also contribute to difficulties in recognizing spatial relationships and correctly using trigonometric formulas. This shows that students have a weak foundation in basic trigonometric concepts and thus, it is essential for Secondary Education students to master their solving skills in trigonometry, particularly on non-triangles, as it has a profound impact on individuals, extending beyond the classroom to real-world applications and future career prospects (Nannumpuni & Retnawati, 2021).

Despite these challenges, there are opportunities for enhancing trigonometry education in the Philippines. The integration of technology, particularly online learning platforms like Khan Academy, offers a potential solution for addressing the shortcomings of traditional teaching methods. Khan Academy, with its vast library of video lessons, interactive exercises, and personalized learning pathways, has emerged as a prominent player in this landscape. Khan Academy was perceived as encouraging independence, available, and more interesting than books; learning math via Khan Academy was more motivating and enjoyable (Vidergor et. al, 2020). This personalized approach contrasts with traditional classroom settings, which often struggle to accommodate the diverse learning styles and paces of students.

A large number of studies have suggested that the use of technology in teaching can improve the acquisition of trigonometric concepts. For example, recent studies by Lee and Kim (2021) show that the use of software for the visualization of trigonometric functions has significantly helped students to better understand the concept of periodicity and graphical representation (Lee & Kim, 2021). Similarly, Jenkins (2022) emphasizes the importance of using computer simulations to help students gain a clear visualization of the changes that occur

when the angles and values of the functions change (Jenkins, 2022). Recent studies have also shown that including hands-on activities in teaching trigonometry, such as constructing graphs and using digital tools, significantly increases students' level of understanding. Research by Garcia and Fernandez (2021) shows that the use of augmented reality applications has improved students' results in trigonometry tests, allowing them to visualize abstract concepts more concretely (Garcia& Fernandez, 2021).

A study conducted by Nguyen et. al (2020) found that students who used Khan Academy resources in their mathematics class showed significant improvement in their test scores compared to those who did not use the resources. Another study conducted by Lee et al. (2020) found that the use of Khan Academy resources in a mathematics class reduced the achievement gap between high- achieving and low- achieving students. Additionally, Diri (2023) found that Khan Academy video-based instruction significantly improved students' performance in mathematics compared to traditional teaching methods. Students exposed to the videos demonstrated higher achievement in mathematics, with male students outperforming female students.

However, the effectiveness of Khan Academy, or any online learning platform, as a supplementary tool is not universally established. Many studies focused on broader measures of academic achievement or general mathematics skills, lacking the specificity needed to assess their impact on the unique challenges presented by trigonometry. This study aimed to investigate the effectiveness of using Khan Academy as a supplementary tool on the performance of Grade 9 students in solving non-right triangles in trigonometry. Specifically, this study seeks to explore whether the integration of Khan Academy resources can improve students' understanding, retention, and application of trigonometric concepts, ultimately enhancing their academic achievement. This study can provide valuable insights into its potential to contribute to the improvement of mathematics education as compared to other studies, which presented general points in addressing these problems. Hence, it delved particularly in the area of trigonometry, in solving non-right triangles using the Law of Sine and Cosines, and in the development of more effective teaching strategies and online learning resources/tools that can improve student performance. This research addresses this gap by focusing specifically on the application of Khan Academy as a supplementary tool.

1.1 Research questions

This study assessed the effectiveness of Khan Academy as a supplementary tool in trigonometry instruction, particularly in solving problems involving non-right Triangles of Grade 9 students in the University of Eastern Philippines, Laoang Laboratory High School, Laoang, Northern Samar

The researchers sought answers to the following study questions:

1. What is the pre-test result of the controlled group and experimental group?
2. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test results of the controlled group and experimental group?
3. What is the post-test result of the controlled group and the experimental group?
4. Is there a significant difference between the post-test results of the controlled group and experimental group?
5. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results of the controlled group?
6. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test of the experimental group?
7. What are the challenges encountered by the students using Khan Academy?
8. What are the students' suggestions for using Khan Academy?

2 Methodology

2.1 Research design

This study used a quasi-experimental research design to assess the effectiveness of Khan Academy on Grade 9 students' problem-solving skills in non-right triangles. Participants were divided into an experimental group using Khan Academy and a control group following traditional methods. A pretest and posttest were conducted to assess initial knowledge and performance. The study also analyzed challenges faced by the experimental

group and their suggestions in using Khan Academy, providing empirical evidence of Khan Academy, providing empirical evidence of Khan Academy's effectiveness in trigonometry instruction.

2.2 Participants

The study involved 29 Grade 9 students from the University of Eastern Philippines Laoang Laboratory High School for the school year 2024-2025, who were divided into an experimental group of 15 students using Khan Academy and a control group of 14 students using traditional methods. Selected students from the experimental group were randomly interviewed to share the challenges they face and their suggestions for using Khan Academy.

2.3 Population and sampling

This study employed a purposive sampling technique. Thus, the Grade 9 students from the University of Eastern Philippines Laoang Laboratory High School, Laoang, Northern Samar, enrolled during the 2024-2025 academic year were selected as participants. Participants were divided into an experimental group using Khan Academy and a control group following traditional instruction. Additionally, ten students from the experimental group who encountered more challenges were selected for an interview to explore the challenges and their suggestions encountered while using Khan Academy.

2.4 Research instrument

To measure the effectiveness of Khan Academy on students' performance, a 15-item test patterned from the DepEd module for Mathematics 9 under Quarter 2: Week 6-7, Module 5, focusing on Illustrating Law of Sines and Cosines, was used to assess students' knowledge and problem-solving skills in non-right triangles. A pretest was given before intervention, after which the experimental group used Khan Academy while the control group followed traditional instruction. The same test served as a posttest to evaluate improvement. Additionally, selected students from the experimental group were interviewed using guide questions to explore challenges, usability, effectiveness, and factors affecting engagement in Khan Academy.

2.5 Data collection

Before conducting the study, researchers secured permission from the school principal and Grade 9 math teachers to select participants and administer the pretest, then divided them into a control group of 14 students following traditional instruction and an experimental group of 15 students using Khan Academy. After the intervention, a posttest was conducted to assess improvement, followed by one-on-one interviews with selected experimental group students, with responses recorded and all data analyzed using appropriate statistical tools.

2.6 Data analysis

The study employed both quantitative and qualitative methods, with a primary emphasis on quantitative analysis through pretest and posttest scores of Grade 9 students from the University of Eastern Philippines Laoang Laboratory High School, analyzed using a t-test to measure the effectiveness of Khan Academy in improving trigonometry performance. Qualitative data from student interviews were examined using thematic analysis to identify common challenges, with key responses coded, categorized, and refined into clear themes that enriched the study's findings.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Pre-test results of controlled and experimental groups

Table 1 presents the pre-test results of the controlled and experimental groups, arranged from the highest to the lowest frequencies.

In the controlled group, 4 (26.7%) achieved scores of 6 and 7, interpreted as “Poor” and “Fair,” respectively. Following this, 2 (13.3%) recorded scores of 3 and 4, categorized as “Very Poor” and “Poor.” Additionally, 1 (6.7%) attained a score of 8, classified as “Fair,” while another 1 (6.7%) scored 5, interpreted as “Poor.” The mean score for the controlled group was 5.6, categorized as “Poor,” with a standard deviation of 1.6. These results indicate a low level of understanding of trigonometry, particularly in solving non-right triangles, before the intervention.

In the experimental group, the highest frequency was observed in scores of 5, attained by 4 (26.7%), categorized as “Poor.” Next, 3 (20.0%) recorded scores of 8 and 9, both interpreted as “Fair.” Additionally, 2 (13.3%) achieved a score of 6, classified as “Poor.” Meanwhile, 1 (6.7%) attained a score of 7, categorized as “Fair,” and another 1 (6.7%) recorded scores of 2 and 4, interpreted as “Very Poor” and “Poor,” respectively. The mean score for the experimental group was 6.5, also interpreted as “Poor,” with a standard deviation of 2.139. While the experimental group exhibited a slightly higher mean score than the control group, this suggests a marginally better initial understanding of trigonometry.

The pre-test results of both groups align with the findings of Velez et al. (2023), which highlight Filipino students' struggles with trigonometry due to limited prior knowledge, insufficient practice, and difficulty visualizing abstract concepts. Additionally, the results support the study of Hokor et al. (2021), which found that high school students frequently make errors in solving trigonometry problems due to misconceptions, particularly during the transformation, processing, and encoding stages of problem-solving. Furthermore, the findings are consistent with Rohima et al. (2020), which emphasized that trigonometry is a challenging subject disconnected from everyday life, making problem-solving difficult. These studies underscore the need for effective supplementary tools, such as Khan Academy, to enhance understanding and performance in trigonometry.

Table 1. Pre-test results of the controlled group and experimental group

Pre-test Result (Controlled Group)				Post-test Result (Experimental Group)			
Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation	Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation
3	2	13.3%	Very Poor	2	1	6.7%	Very Poor
4	2	13.3%	Poor	4	1	6.7%	Poor
5	1	6.7%	Poor	5	4	26.7%	Poor
6	4	26.7%	Poor	6	2	13.3%	Poor
7	4	26.7%	Fair	7	1	6.7%	Fair
8	1	6.7%	Fair	8	3	20.0%	Fair
				9	3	20.0%	Fair
Mean: 5.643				Mean: 6.500			
Std. Dev.: 1.598				Std. Dev.: 2.139			

3.2 Test of difference between the pre-test results of controlled group and experimental group

Table 2 presents the statistical comparison of pre-test results between the control and experimental groups. The t-test analysis yielded a t-value of -1.295 and a p-value of 0.218, with the significance level set at 0.05. Based on these results, the null hypothesis was not rejected, indicating no statistically significant difference between the pre-test scores of the two groups. This suggests that both groups had a comparable level of understanding of trigonometry before the intervention using Khan Academy.

These findings align with the study by Arhin et al. (2021), which highlighted students' conceptual difficulties in trigonometry, particularly when working with non-right-angled triangles. Additionally, research by Haggara et al. (2024) identified common errors in transformation and process skills when solving trigonometric problems, attributing these mistakes to weaknesses in basic arithmetic operations. Students often struggle with interpreting problem statements, applying trigonometric concepts, and accurately comparing angles. Furthermore, unfamiliarity with trigonometry problems frequently leads to confusion and errors in problem-solving.

Table 2. Significant difference between the pre-test results of the controlled group and experimental group

Variables	t - value	p - value	Level of Significance	Decision	Interpretation
Pre-test (Controlled Group) and Pre-test (Experimental Group)	-1.295	0.218	0.05	Failed to Reject Null Hypothesis	Not Significant

3.3 Post-test results of controlled and experimental groups

Table 3 presents the post-test results of the controlled and experimental groups, arranged from the highest to the lowest frequencies.

In the controlled group, 5 (35.7%) achieved a score of 9, interpreted as “Fair.” Following this, 3 (21.4%) obtained a score of 10, categorized as “Good.” Additionally, 2 (14.3%) recorded scores of 11, also classified as “Good.” Meanwhile, 2 (14.3%) attained scores of 7 and 8, both interpreted as “Fair.” The mean score for the controlled group was 9.071, categorized as “Fair,” with a standard deviation of 1.269. These results indicate a significant improvement in post-test scores compared to pre-test scores, suggesting that the intervention contributed to a more consistent understanding of trigonometry within the controlled group.

In the experimental group, the highest frequency was observed in scores of 14, attained by 6 (40.0%), categorized as “Very Good.” Next, 3 (20.0%) recorded a score of 10, interpreted as “Good.” Additionally, 2 (13.3%) achieved a score of 12, also classified as “Good.” Meanwhile, 1 (6.7%) attained scores of 8 and 9, both interpreted as “Fair.” Furthermore, 1 (6.7%) obtained scores of 5 and 3, categorized as “Poor” and “Very Poor,” respectively. The mean score for the experimental group was 11.000, interpreted as “Good,” with a standard deviation of 3.595. These results indicate a significant improvement in post-test scores compared to pre-test scores, suggesting that the intervention led to a substantial enhancement in the understanding of trigonometry within the experimental group.

The findings align with the study of Garcia (2023), which emphasized that even traditional teaching approaches, when combined with clear explanations, structured problem-solving activities, and real-life examples, can significantly enhance students’ comprehension of trigonometric concepts. This is consistent with previous studies by Cabugwason et al. (2024) and Nguyen et al. (2020), which found that math applications serve as valuable supplements to teacher-led instruction (Pala et al, 2025), helping students gain a deeper understanding of complex concepts. These applications, which incorporate graphs and other visual aids, assist learners in grasping the relationships between mathematical topics. Additionally, the findings highlight that using Khan Academy in mathematics classes improves student motivation and performance due to its clear structure, self-paced modules, and accessible learning tools.

Table 3. Post-test results of the controlled group and experimental group

Post-test Result (Controlled Group)				Post-test Result (Experimental Group)			
Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation	Scores	Frequency	Percentage	Interpretation
7	2	14.3%	Fair	3	1	6.7%	Very Poor
8	2	14.3%	Fair	5	1	6.7%	Poor
9	5	35.3%	Fair	8	1	6.7%	Fair
10	3	21.4%	Good	9	1	6.7%	Fair
11	2	14.3%	Good	10	3	20.0%	Good
				12	2	13.3%	Good
				14	6	40.0%	Very Good
Mean: 9.071				Mean: 11.000			
Std. Dev.: 1.269				Std. Dev.: 3.595			

3.4 Test of difference between the post-test results of controlled group and experimental group

Table 4 presents the statistical comparison of post-test results between the control and experimental groups. The t-test analysis yielded a t-value of -1.791 and a p-value of 0.097, with the significance level set at 0.05. Based on these results, the null hypothesis was not rejected, indicating no statistically significant difference between the post-test scores of the two groups. This suggests that the intervention, whether or not Khan Academy was used as a supplementary tool, resulted in similar learning outcomes. Consequently, the use of Khan Academy did not lead to a demonstrably better outcome compared to traditional instruction alone.

These findings align with the studies of Devers et al. (2014) and Diri (2023), which observed that while students showed significant improvement in their post-test scores after engaging with Khan Academy videos, further research is needed to assess their long-term effectiveness. Their conclusions suggest that traditional instruction remains a viable teaching method. Additionally, Ayaz (2023) found that students who utilized online platforms demonstrated academic improvement, with Khan Academy’s gamification features serving as a motivating factor. Online educational technologies have been shown to positively impact student motivation and learning outcomes, particularly in under-resourced communities.

However, these findings contrast with the study by Diri (2023), which reported that students taught using Khan Academy videos outperformed those who received conventional instruction. This discrepancy highlights the need for further investigation into the effectiveness of Khan Academy as a supplementary learning tool in different educational contexts.

Table 4. Test of difference between the post-test results of controlled group and experimental group

1	t - value	p - value	Level of Significance	Decision	Interpretation
Post-test (controlled) and Post-test Results (Experimental)	-1.791	0.097	0.05	Failed to Reject Null Hypothesis	Not Significant

3.5 Test of difference between the pre-test and post-test results of controlled group

Table 5 presents the statistical comparison between the pre-test and post-test results of the control group. The t-test analysis yielded a t-value of -7.186 and a p-value of 0.000, with the significance level set at 0.05. Based on these results, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a statistically significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the control group. This suggests that the intervention led to a substantial improvement in students' understanding of trigonometry within the control group.

These findings underscore the effectiveness of traditional instruction in enhancing students' comprehension of trigonometric concepts, particularly when they begin with a relatively low baseline. Research supports the importance of teacher quality in mathematics education, emphasizing the need for educators to address common misconceptions and utilize clear explanations and visual aids (Garcia, 2023). Additionally, Francisco (2020) found that instructional methods significantly influence student performance, though the extent of their impact varies. His study explored different teaching strategies and their effects on student achievement, acknowledging that traditional methods continue to play a crucial role in shaping learning outcomes.

Table 5. Test of difference between the pre-test and post-test results of the controlled group

Variables	t - value	p - value	Level of Significance	Decision	Interpretation
Posttest and Pre-test Results	-7.186	0.000	0.05	Reject the Null Hypothesis	Significant

3.6 Test of difference between the pre-test and post-test results of the experimental group

Table 6 presents the statistical comparison between the pre-test and post-test results of the experimental group. The t-test analysis yielded a t-value of -4.198 and a p-value of 0.001, with the significance level set at 0.05.

Based on these results, the null hypothesis was rejected, indicating a statistically significant difference between the pre-test and post-test scores of the experimental group. This suggests that the intervention led to a substantial improvement in students' understanding of trigonometry within the experimental group.

These findings support the study by Lee et al. (2021), which found that the use of Khan Academy resources in mathematics instruction helped reduce the achievement gap between high-achieving and low-achieving students. Additionally, the results align with the findings of Tugas (2023), which demonstrated that integrating Khan Academy into the teaching of geometry and trigonometry contributed to enhanced student performance in understanding trigonometric concepts. These studies highlight the effectiveness of Khan Academy as a supplementary learning tool in improving mathematical competence.

Furthermore, Diri (2023) found that video-based instruction through Khan Academy significantly improved students' performance in mathematics compared to traditional teaching methods. Students exposed to Khan Academy videos demonstrated higher achievement, with male students outperforming female students. However, while Khan Academy has shown promise in enhancing mathematical learning, further research is needed to explore its long-term impact and effectiveness across different student populations and instructional settings.

Table 6. Test of difference between the pre-test and post-test results of the experimental group

Variables	t - value	p - value	Level of Significance	Decision	Interpretation
Posttest and Pre-test Results	-4.198	0.001	0.05	Reject the Null Hypothesis	Significant

3.7 Challenges encountered in using the khan academy

Thematic analysis revealed key challenges encountered in using Khan Academy, including navigation and usability, content accessibility and searchability, assessment and feedback mechanisms, technical issues, and diverse user experiences.

3.7.1 Navigational and usability issues

The platform's interface can be overwhelming for some users, especially those unfamiliar with online learning environments. The abundance of buttons and options can lead to confusion about how to navigate effectively. Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"I had a bit of difficulty because there were so many buttons to click,"
"It was a bit confusing at first since I'm not very familiar with the app,"

This aligns with the study of Xue et al. (2023) found that the ease of navigation and usability of an online platform directly influenced its perceived usefulness and enhanced students' educational experience. Additionally, Vlasenko et al. (2020) emphasized that well-structured navigation and high usability in online math courses significantly contribute to user satisfaction and efficient learning. Sidhawara (2023) revealed that effective navigational elements significantly improved task performance and overall user satisfaction. However, Nobis et al (2024) barriers such as unstable internet access, financial constraints, and digital competence impacted their learning experiences.

3.7.2 Content accessibility and searchability

Users struggle to find specific lessons or content, suggesting potential issues with the search functionality or content organization. Some users feel that the content available is insufficient, further hindering their ability to find the information they need.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme

"I still find it difficult to search for them because I can't immediately find what I'm looking for"
"Sometimes the content shown there also feels like it lacks."

Sheikh et. al (2021) found that Users faced difficulty navigating Khan Academy due to inadequate search functionalities and interface complexity. The platform scored 71.5 on the System Usability Scale, indicating acceptable usability but clear room for improvement. Additionally, Vats (2024) found that the Khan Academy app revealed issues with content discoverability and personalization, especially among female users, resulting in reduced engagement and satisfaction. Also, the NYU UX design team (2020) found that the redesign for screen reader accessibility improved navigation and content clarity for blind users, highlighting gaps in Khan Academy's accessibility support and the importance of inclusive design. The most prominent barriers identified were limited financial resources and the lack of readily available computer laboratories and instructional software/electronic resources (Nobis, 2025).

3.7.3 Assessment and feedback mechanism

The platform's requirement for exact answers in exercises can be frustrating, as it doesn't align with traditional teaching methods that often allow for some flexibility in answers. Issues with video completion tracking can also cause frustration, making students feel like their progress wasn't being accurately recognized.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"The app requires the answer to be specific."

"It still didn't mark the video as completed and just kept asking me to watch it again,".

This aligns with Louro (2025), which highlighted that while gamification elements like points and badges can enhance motivation, the platform's strict assessment criteria and lack of flexibility in accepting varied correct answers may counteract these benefits, potentially leading to user frustration. Al Hashimi (2022) found that students reported frustration with online assessments due to unclear instructions, insufficient feedback, and a lack of personal interaction, making it harder to understand expectations and improve. Additionally, Flores (2024) emphasized that timely and clear feedback significantly reduced students' perceived difficulty in online learning, pointing to feedback as a key factor in learner motivation and success.

3.7.4 Technical issues and platform's stability

Users report technical problems, such as errors, logging issues, and application crashes. These frustrations suggest that the app may not be functioning optimally for all users, which can disrupt the learning experience. Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"When I log in, sometimes I get logged out and redirected back to the browser."

"The Google account sign-up didn't work at first, but trying another sign-in method worked."

"The videos don't register as completed even if I've already watched them."

"I ended up finishing the answers at 2 a.m." (indicating time spent due to technical issues)

"I encountered a problem while I was answering a quiz or practice — it suddenly crashed."

This supports Ali (2023), who found that gamification features in Khan Academy increased short-term engagement but lacked user-centered design, which limited long-term motivation and inclusivity for students in under-resourced, high-ELL communities. Agtarap et al. (2024) found that teachers struggled with ensuring authentic and fair assessments in online learning, highlighting problems such as poor feedback quality and difficulties tracking actual student progress. Additionally, Bond (2020) found that blogs, mobile learning, and assessment tools like Khan Academy were the most effective at promoting engagement, however, caution and education in how to use technology are needed, as any use not underpinned by effective and informed pedagogy can also lead to students feeling overwhelmed and disengaging from learning.

3.7.5 Diverse user experiences and satisfaction levels

While some users report no major issues and express satisfaction, others highlight significant challenges, indicating a diverse range of experiences with the platform.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"I haven't had any difficulties with it."

"I don't experience major issues."

"I often get logged out and redirected in the browser."

"I haven't used any other educational apps aside from Duolingo, which is more for learning languages like Japanese. For me, it's just okay — it's not difficult or confusing to use."

"I don't usually use other learning apps; I prefer traditional methods like books."

This supports to Yu (2022) found that different learners have different motivations for online learning, different expectations of support from online instructors, different perceptions of usefulness and convenience of online courses, and different levels of OLS. Therefore, the research subjects of future research should be expanded to focus on online learners from all social strata. Additionally, Olatunbosun et. Al (2024) Research emphasized the importance of addressing diverse student needs and experiences in online learning environments to improve satisfaction levels and learning outcomes. Students have different satisfaction levels when it comes to online learning, like Khan Academy. Almusharraf et. al (2024) found that students appreciated webinars, seminars, and extracurricular activities, recognizing their importance in enriching online education. However, they wanted more than school-provided facilities, suggesting physical resources and service improvements.

The results imply that the challenges encountered by students using Khan Academy highlight the importance of considering the platform's limitations and the need for proper training and support for both teachers and students. This suggests that while Khan Academy can be a valuable resource, it should be used strategically and with careful consideration of its potential drawbacks.

3.8 What are the students' suggestions for using khan academy?

Users give various suggestions for using Khan Academy, which include enhancing technical stability and user experience, strengthening educational content and teaching quality and increasing accessibility and Learning Flexibility.

3.8.1 Enhancing technical stability and user experience

A smooth and reliable platform is essential for effective learning. Users have highlighted various technical issues that disrupt their experience, such as frequent logouts, browser redirections, and inaccurate video completion tracking. Addressing these bugs and optimizing the app's performance would create a more seamless and frustration-free environment for learners.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"I hope they fix the bugs or the errors so that our learning using the app will be smooth."

"I often get logged out and redirected in the browser."

"Improve the video playback so it correctly marks the video as completed."

This supports Sheikh et al. (2021), who found that Khan Academy has strong usability overall, but there are areas needing improvement, particularly in navigation and interface consistency, to enhance user-centered learning experiences. Additionally, Lysenko et al. (2023) identified technical issues such as unstable internet access and lack of user support as key barriers to effective online learning, highlighting the need for more robust platforms and support systems.

3.8.2 Strengthening educational content and teaching quality

A rich and well-structured curriculum is the foundation of effective learning. Users have expressed the need for a broader range of topics, more comprehensive lessons, and clearer instructional videos. Some lessons feel incomplete, leaving gaps in understanding. Improving the quality of teaching—through clearer explanations and better-structured content—would greatly enhance comprehension and overall learning effectiveness.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme:

"They should add more features or more lessons for certain subjects.

"Sometimes the lessons shown feel incomplete, and there are topics that I don't know or can't find.

"I suggest improving the teaching aspect, as I noticed some videos were confusing, and I didn't understand them well.

This supports Khoza (2022), which revealed that improving teaching quality in online environments requires interactive methods, continuous feedback, and teacher training to adapt to digital pedagogy effectively. Additionally, Maan (2023) found that the digital content component highlights the importance of open educational resources, digital libraries, and virtual labs to support learning. It addresses the need for training and upskilling educators and administrators to implement digital solutions effectively.

3.8.3 Increasing accessibility and learning flexibility

To cater to diverse learners, the platform should provide greater adaptability. Many users struggle with rigid answer formats and language barriers. Allowing slight variations in responses and expanding language options would make the platform more inclusive. Additionally, providing accessible learning resources, such as external links, would help users navigate complex topics with greater ease.

Here are some examples of responses that reflect this theme

*"They should allow a bit of flexibility, like allowing slight variations in answers."**

"The availability of links and languages would be helpful, as sometimes I struggle with pure English."

Accessibility and learning flexibility of Khan Academy should be addressed for a more effective learning environment, as having online platforms that are flexible and personalized can support the learning of students. This aligns with Almusharraf (2020), who highlighted the importance of instructor support, guidance, and personalization in the online learning environment. Also, Radjapov (2024) and Nobis & Caparoso (2024) found that interactive features and personalized feedback in online platforms significantly boost student engagement and learning outcomes.

4 Conclusion

The study found that participants from the controlled group and experimental group had a poor level of understanding of solving non-right triangles based on their pre-test results. This implies that the respondents have a poor level of understanding of trigonometry, specifically in solving non-right triangles, before the intervention.

The results also found that there was no statistically significant difference between the pre-test scores of the two groups. This implies that both controlled and experimental groups had a similar level of understanding of trigonometry before introducing the intervention, Khan Academy.

Additionally, the post-test results revealed that the controlled group had a "fair" understanding of solving non-right triangles, while the post-test results of the experimental group revealed "good". This indicates a significant improvement in the post-test scores compared to the pre-test scores. It implies that the traditional instruction and intervention of Khan Academy led to a significant improvement in the understanding of trigonometry amongst the controlled and experimental groups.

Further, the results found that there was no statistically significant difference between the post-test scores of the two groups. This means that the intervention, regardless of whether Khan Academy was used as a supplementary tool, led to similar levels of learning outcomes. This implies that the use of Khan Academy as a supplementary tool did not lead to a demonstrably better outcome compared to traditional instruction alone.

Based on the findings, there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results of a controlled group. This implies that even traditional instruction can lead to significant improvements in trigonometry understanding, especially when students start with a relatively low baseline.

Also, it was found that there is a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results of the experimental group, suggesting that the intervention led to a significant improvement in the understanding of trigonometry amongst the experimental group.

Thematic analysis revealed key challenges encountered in using Khan Academy, including navigation and usability, content accessibility and searchability, assessment and feedback mechanisms, technical issues, and diverse user experiences. Also, participants' suggestions include enhancing technical stability and user experience, strengthening educational content and teaching quality, and increasing accessibility and learning flexibility. The results imply that the challenges encountered by students using Khan Academy highlight the importance of considering the platform's limitations and the need for proper training and support for both teachers and students.

Disclaimer (Artificial Intelligence)

This research utilized ChatGPT, CiCi, and Copilot—advanced AI language models—for paraphrasing paragraphs and checking grammatical errors. The free ChatGPT app, along with Cici and Copilot, was employed as a tool to enhance the clarity and readability of the text, ensuring that ideas were effectively communicated while maintaining the original meaning. The use of these AI models contributed to refining the language and structure of the manuscript.

Details of the AI usage are given below:

1. Used ChatGPT, Cici, and Copilot for paraphrasing paragraphs to improve the clarity and readability of the text.
2. Used ChatGPT, Cici, and Copilot for checking language and grammar to enhance overall accuracy and fluency.

Ethical Approval and Consent

This study prioritized ethical considerations by securing permission from school officials and informed consent from all participants, who were made aware of the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to withdraw at any time. Interviews were recorded and transcribed accurately, while anonymity and confidentiality were strictly maintained. Potential biases were addressed, and the research followed institutional ethical guidelines to protect participants' rights and well-being.

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Competing Interests

Authors have declared that no competing interests exist.

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